

paper Chain

Performance of Circular Case 1. Asphalt and
concrete applications

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New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

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0. Executive summary

Deliverable D5.6 "Performance of Circular Case 1 (CC1) Asphalt and concrete applications" aims to show the results of mid-term assessment of technical and environmental performance of the two demonstrators implemented in Portugal (CC1a - concrete structure application and CC1b - asphalt road application). This report belongs to WP5 which aimed to build and validate, at industrial scale, the replacement of natural fillers and aggregates by lime ash in precast concrete formulations and green liquor dregs and grits in asphalt mixtures for road pavements.

The Portuguese circular case (CC1) covered the incorporation of PPI wastes in 2 types of construction materials. In circular case CC1a the filler in precast concrete formulations was completely replaced by lime ash. In circular case CC1b the fine aggregate in bituminous mixtures for road pavements were partially replaced by dregs or grits. Regarding CC1a, two different precast concrete formulations designed for columns and beams (C20/25 and C30/37 strength classes, respectively) were set as reference and were used for total replacement of the natural filler by the PPI waste (lime ash). The production time of columns and beams were monitored to be the same for natural filler-based concrete and lime ash based concrete formulations. The 3 porticos, plus the reference one, were built and finished in time to carry on with the planned monitoring processes in time, one year. Until now, the compared characteristics revealed no different behaviour when compared with the reference.

Regarding CC1B, the reference bituminous mixture formulation was an AC14 road surface class type, where the natural filler and fine aggregate were partially replaced by dregs or grits (PPI wastes). The incorporation and application on site went well. There was just a week delay on the final application due to raining, but it was quickly solved next week (March 6). The different formulations, the reference plus the ones containing grits or dregs, were applied in a 250 m road surface as planned to be monitored and controlled for a long term period (*visual, technical and environmental features control*). Production features and time were not altered by these wastes incorporation. By comparing the different bituminous mixtures (reference and with dregs and grits incorporation) no significant performance deviations were observed.

The licence process took longer time that was initial foreseen which delayed the demos construction and the monitoring process. Even so, without hinder the proposed plan. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown caused some delays on monitoring plans which required the adjustment of the program in order to complete all the planned tasks (an extension of 3 months was needed in the WP5 stage).

Keywords

Real Scale	Demonstrator	Implementation	Asphalt	Performance
Precast concrete	Lime ash	Green liquor dregs	Grits	Monitoring

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Abbreviations and acronyms:

AC: asphalt concrete

IP: Infrastructures of Portugal

PPI: Pulp and Paper Industry

COD: Chemical Oxygen Demand

QI: Quality index

1. Introduction

The Paperchain project has allowed extending the work that the University of Aveiro and Navigator/Raiz have been doing together during the last years for the evaluation and conversion of these sub-products into new raw materials. From the several R&D and pilot projects with academic and industrial partners, dregs, grits and lime ash are the most difficult PPI wastes to valorise.

Previous research on these PPI wastes conducted by NVG and University of Aveiro (UAVR) has shown that it is possible to incorporate them in several construction materials replacing aggregates or fillers without hindering the final products technical performance. This could result in relevant environmental and economic benefits due to the reduction of landfill disposal as well as the savings in natural raw materials. Moreover, the centre region of Portugal has a strong manufacturing sector for construction products, creating a good potential for industrial symbiosis. These Paperchain demos are a good example to show and replicate for other sectors the added value of valorisation of wastes as alternative raw materials based in a circular way of thinking.

The Portuguese circular case cover two types of construction materials. In circular case CC1a the natural filler in precast concrete is completely replaced by lime ash. In circular case CC1b the fine aggregates in bituminous mixtures are partial replaced by dregs and grits.

These new products were produced in industrial conditions and applied on a real scale to evaluate their environmental and technical performance after application during this project. During the production stage and after the 2 pilots installation, there was an extensive monitoring stage aiming to verify that precast concrete with lime ash and bituminous mixture with dregs or grits have the same quality and behaviour than precast concrete with natural filler and asphalt with natural aggregates, respectively. This deliverable 5.6 is set to show the results of the assessment of performance and the final conclusions of the implementation.

1.1. Objectives

The Paperchain project aims to demonstrate the technical, environmental and economic feasibility of using some wastes from pulp and paper industries (PPI) in different sectors (construction, mining and chemical). In Portugal, the project was set to test and evaluate products using three PPI wastes (green liquor dregs, grits and lime ash) as secondary raw materials for the construction sector. The Portuguese circular case involves the construction of two demonstrator pilots (CC1a and CC1b) related to the application of wastes in the production of precast concrete and bituminous mixtures for road construction, respectively. In the work package WP5, related to the execution of these 2 pilots at industrial scale, the last task (5.6) addresses to the monitoring of the built structures with which this deliverable is directly concerned.

1.2. Circular Cases

1.2.1 Circular case 1a) Precast concrete

The precast concrete pilot (CC1a) involved the production and assembly of four porticos (columns and beams) of an industrial pavilion. One portico was produced with two SPRAL reference concrete formulations, one composition for columns and other composition for beams. The remaining structure was also produced with the same formulations, but the natural filler was fully replaced by lime ash.

Lime ash, from the Navigator mill was sent to SPRAL (precast concrete producer) manufacturing unit without any pre-treatment. This waste is physically and chemically very similar to the natural filler used in SPRAL concrete production and the only critical step was the transportation from Navigator to SPRAL due to its fine particle size. The transport of this material is made through a tanker truck and placed into a silo that allows the introduction of the material directly in the precast concrete production. Transport was carried out by a licensed waste manager (Dilumex).

Before the installation of demonstrator, the pilot also needed an environmental licence (Unique Environmental Title (TUA)) to implement it. The licensing followed the Portuguese decree law n° 178/2006.

Each precast concrete column had a (0.5*0.4) m section, a 10.25 m of height, corresponding to a volume of 2.1 m³ of a C30/37 class precast concrete. On the other hand, each variable beam section had a (0.4*0.56) m section at the support and a (0.4*1.4) m of section at ½ half span. These beams had 19.8 m of length, corresponding to 5 m³ of a C40/45 class precast concrete. The four porticos were set at five meters apart.

1.2.2. Circular case 1B) Asphalt pavement

The asphalt pavement (CC1b) involved the use of an AC 14 bituminous mixture on a road surface layer. The pilot was divided into four different segments, to test three compositions containing dregs and grits plus the reference one with natural aggregates. This reference bituminous composition, also type AC14, used granite gravel as coarse aggregate (6/14mm), calcareous and granite crushed aggregate (0/5mm), commercial filler and a bitumen 50/70. The abovementioned PPI wastes replaced 4% of crushed limestone fine aggregate.

The PPI wastes integrated on the bituminous mixtures (dregs and grits) required a pre-treatment to be used in the final mixture. In this case, the dregs and grits were transported from Navigator mill (NVG Pulp Aveiro) to a licenced waste manager (Dilumex) in order to proceed with the pre-treatment. The wastes pre-treatment consisted of drying and sieving (particles smaller than 10 millimetres). After the pre-treatment, the same waste manager transported the treated wastes to the bituminous central.

The bituminous mixture central produced the standard AC14 bituminous mixture and the waste-based bituminous mixture (with dregs or grits). The different bituminous mixtures were transported by Megavia, the road pavement industrial partner, from the bituminous central to Navigator where the different bituminous mixtures were applied in different sections.

Before the installation of the demonstrator, an environmental licence (Unique Environmental Title (TUA)) was also required to implement it. The licensing followed the Portuguese decree law n° 178/2006.

The pilot design was set and planned to apply 2800 m² of different bituminous mixtures (AC 14 surface) on a 250 m road section that was divided into the following road partial stretches with both linear and curved sections:

- 640 m² of reference bituminous mixture
- 1440 m² of bituminous mixture with grits
- 720 m² of bituminous mixture with dregs

2. Circular case 1a: Precast concrete

Precast elements were built on December 2019 and January 2020 and it took place in SPRAL installation at Ílhavo (Figure 1). The pavilion was assembled and Figure 2 shows the final porticos. From then until now, there was 1 year of monitoring procedures set in the project.

FIGURE 1. INSTALLATION LOCAL OF PORTICOS.

FIGURE 2. FINAL PORTICOS.

2.1. Monitoring

During the beams and columns production, concrete samples (cubes 150*150*150mm³) with natural filler and lime ash were collected and stored to evaluate their performance at ages of 7, 28, 180 and 365 days of curing, which were tested each time at the laboratory. In addition, sensors were also installed in beams to collect data about strain and temperature with time. They were logged in fifteen days after beams casting and after assembling the porticos' structure.

The monitoring periodic involved environmental and technical parameters besides the visual observation of the entire structure.

2.1.1. Environmental monitoring.

A rapid test with indicator paper was used to measure, and follow in time, the pH of the concrete columns. This test started after assembling the porticos and the weather in Ílhavo was also monitored. The pH for lime ash and reference precast concrete was observed to remain around 8-9 (Figure 3).

FIGURE 3. PH FOR LIME ASH AND REFERENCE CONCRETE.

Control of soluble salts for all compositions was also evaluated with a wet/dry cycle using concrete specimens which are used to measure water absorption. All concrete samples with 28, 180 and 365 days of curing showed no efflorescence on its surface (Figure 4).

FIGURE 4. CONCRETE EFFLORESCENCE CONTROL

After the compressive strength test (at 7, 28, 180 and 365 days of curing), the exposed surface of all samples was sprayed with phenolphthalein to analyse the hydration degree (related to portlandite production revealed by its carbonation). The visual

inspection shows high degree of hydration, as can be seen in Figure 5. Purple colour appear when portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) is present as an hydration product. If portlandite carbonation had occurred it would have turned to no colour. It is possible to observe the same intensity of purple in both natural filler and fly ash containing concrete compositions.

FIGURE 5. HYDRATION DEGREE CONTROL

2.1.2. Technical monitoring

Reference concrete with natural aggregates (sand, gravel, filler) and cement have CE marking, which means that its characteristics such as density, particle size are declared on the product technical sheet. Thus, lime ash and filler were characterized in the laboratory to observe any difference between them.

Figure 6 shows visual inspection between lime ash and natural filler.

FIGURE 6. VISUAL COMPARATIVE BETWEEN LIME ASH AND FILLER.

Figure 7 presents particle size distribution for lime ash and filler. This analysis demonstrates that lime ash complies with grading requirements for the filler role,

according to EN 12620, which establishes 70, 80 and 100% as the minimum of material passing on sieves 0.063, 0.125 and 2 mm, respectively.

FIGURE 7. PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF FILLER AND LIME ASH.

Table 1 and Figure 8 show also a quite similar particle size distribution (lime ash and natural limestone filler) below 63 µm performed with a Coulter particle size analyser.

TABLE 1. FILLER AND LIME ASH PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION.

%V	Size µm	
	Lime ash	Filler
10	0,648	0,232
25	3,023	1,149
50	7,992	2,725
75	15,12	5,615
90	22,12	15,19

FIGURE 8. FILER AND LIME ASH PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION.

Filler and lime ash have a specific surface area of 1,156 and 0,786 m²/g, respectively, as determined by BET method.

The XRD pattern of the natural filler and lime ash is shown in Figure 9. The composition of the sample according to the XRD analysis is as follows (Table 2).

TABLE 2. THE COMPOSITION OF THE LIME ASH AND FILER.

Mineral phase	Chemical compound	Natural Filler	Lime ash
Calcite	Calcium carbonate (CaCO ₃)	100	96
Lime	Calcium Oxide (CaO)	0	4

Particle density for lime ash and filler is 2,60 and 2,66 g/cm³, respectively. Fine particles quality is also evaluated through the blue methylene test and this parameter must be below 2g/kg (according to E 467: Guide for use of aggregates in concrete). The blue methylene value for lime ash and filler is 0,1 and 0,2 g/kg, respectively, so, lime ash is within the specification limit for a filler.

FIGURE 9. THE XRD PATTERN OF THE A) FILLER AND B) OF THE LIME ASH.

Beams and columns were manufactured on a production line of SPRAL industrial facilities and cubic specimens (150x150x150 mm³ size) were taken directly from their batches and moulded during production to perform the established laboratory control. Figure 10 shows the samples inside the moulds during element production and stored for curing afterwards in a chamber at 20°C of temperature and 95% of relative humidity.

a) b)
FIGURE 10. A) CONCRETE SAMPLES FOR MONITORING TESTS; B) CURING OF CONCRETE.

In laboratory, some parameters were measured, namely, the density of hardened concrete samples for all compositions (Figure 11) was measured at 7, 28, 180 and 365 days following the procedure of the European Standard EN 12390-7.

FIGURE 11. DENSITY OF HARDENED CONCRETE FOR: A) COLUMNS AND B) BEAMS.

The compressive strength for all compositions (Figure 12) was also taken at 7, 28, 180 and 365 days following the procedure according to EN 12390-3. This harmonized standard for precast concrete establishes a minimum compressive strength class for beams and columns. At the beginning of the pilot design it was defined to be C30/37 and C40/45 for columns and beams as a reference, respectively.

FIGURE 12. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH DEVELOPMENT OF CONCRETES OVER CURING TIME: A) COLUMNS; B) BEAMS.

The elastic modulus determination was made using a nondestructive testing (PUNDIT - Portable Ultrasonic Non-Destructive Indicating Tester) for all compositions (Figure 13), and performed at 28, 180 and 365 days following the European Standard EN 12504-4. In this test, the ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) through the sample, showed in table 3, allowed the calculation of the elastic modulus for these samples and the assessment on the quality of the precast concrete. Figure 13 shows that both the samples containing the waste and the reference sample containing the natural filler reveal very close values.

TABLE 3. QUALITY CONCRETE BASED ON UPV VALUES.

Concrete quality	UPV (km/s)
Excellent	> 4,5
Good	3,6 -4,5
Questionable	3,0 -3,6
Poor	2,1-3,0
Very Poor	<2,1

a)

b)

c)

d)

FIGURE 13. EVALUATION OF: A) ULTRASONIC PULSE VELOCITY VALUES AND B) ELASTICITY MODULUS FOR COLUMNS; C) ULTRASONIC PULSE VELOCITY VALUES AND D) ELASTICITY MODULUS FOR BEAMS;

a)

b)

FIGURE 14. WATER ABSORPTION BEHAVIOUR FOR: A) COLUMNS AND B) COLUMNS.

Water absorption was also measured for all compositions (Figure 14) at 28, 180 and 365 days following the procedure in E394 (Portuguese specification). Quite similar open porosity values also characterized both formulations.

Capillarity coefficient for all compositions was measured in these samples at 28, 180 and 365 days. The water capillary absorption coefficient was measured according to EN 1015-18 European standard. The capillary absorption coefficient C is the water mass absorbed per unit time, through a unitary surface of a dried sample in contact with a water layer. Figure 15 also shows similar values for both concrete formulations.

FIGURE 15. CAPILLARITY COEFFICIENT (WATER ABSORPTION BY CAPILLARITY) A) COLUMNS AND B) BEAMS.

In situ monitoring was made visually but also through the installation of internal and external sensors in the precast concrete beams. The internal sensors were placed on 1/2 and 1/3 of span and both were placed a depth of 10 cm below the concrete beam surface (Figure 16).

FIGURE 16. INTERNAL SENSOR: A) 1/2 OF BEAM SPAN; B) 1/3 OF BEAM SPAN.

FIGURE 17. RESULTS OF THE TEMPERATURE FROM CASTING TO JANUARY 31TH: A) SENSOR 1/2 OF SPAN; B) SENSOR 1/3 OF SPAN.

Lime ash and reference beam were cast in January 16 and 17, 2020, respectively. The internal sensors were turned on a data logger that register the temperature and frequency values. Afterwards, the frequency values are converted to microstrain ($\mu\epsilon$) through a calibration method. On January 20, 2020, the bars tension was transmitted by adherence to the concrete. On January 31 the data acquisition system was turned off to store the beams in expedition site, to unlock and free the precast lines in use.

Figure 17 and 18 show temperature and strain, respectively, that were monitored through the sensors placed on casting until January 31. At the early age, the temperature and strain are very similar for beams with lime ash and filler.

a)

b)

FIGURE 18. RESULTS OF THE STRAIN FROM CASTING TO JANUARY 31TH: A) SENSOR 1/2 OF SPAN; B) SENSOR 1/3 OF SPAN.

The concrete elements (columns and beams) to assemble the porticos were at the expedition site until February 18th of 2020 and the final structure was completely assembled on February 24. Weldable and embedment sensors in the reference and lime ash beam, as well as an external sensor that measures air temperature and relative humidity (RH) were logged on March 23 (Figure 19) for measurements through time.

Three weldable sensors were also installed at half span and at a beam position of upper, middle and below (Figure 20).

FIGURE 19. A) EXTERNAL SENSOR THAT RECORDS THE AIR TEMPERATURE AND RELATIVE HUMIDITY, B) DATA LOGGER THAT RECORDS FREQUENCY AND TEMPERATURE OF WELDABLE AND EMBEDMENT SENSORS

FIGURE 20. A) EXTERNAL SENSOR (1/2 OF SPAN); B) POSITION (UPPER, MIDDLE, BELOW)

After turning on the acquisition system on the porticos, the air temperature, relative humidity, interior and exterior temperature of beams were logged in during 1-year monitoring (in Figure 21). After assembly, the temperature was very similar for beams with lime ash and filler concrete. Figure 22 shows the longitudinal displacement that the data logger recorded after beams assembly.

a)

b)

c)

d)

FIGURE 21. 1-YEAR MONITORING RESULTS ON: A) AIR TEMPERATURE (EXTERNAL SENSOR); B) RELATIVE HUMIDITY (EXTERNAL SENSOR); C) EXTERNAL TEMPERATURE (WELDABLE SENSORS) AND D) INTERIOR TEMPERATURE (EMBEDMENT SENSORS).

a)

b)

c)

d)

e)

FIGURE 22. RESULTS OF THE A) STRAIN OF 1/2 SPAN; B) STRAIN OF 1/3 SPAN; C) STRAIN OF UPPER SENSOR); D) STRAIN OF MIDDLE SENSOR; AND E) STRAIN OF BELOW SENSOR.

After assembly, the strain that was measured by the internal sensors is very similar for both beams. In the external sensors, there was a deviation between both beams that could be mainly explained by relatively different sun exposure.

Additional technical parameters (Figure 23) were also evaluated in situ with non-destructive testing apparatus (Schmidt hammer and PUNDIT), namely the surface compressive strength (SCS) and the elastic modulus (E). Table 4 shows the values of surface compressive strength (SCS) and elasticity modulus (E) for reference and lime ash concrete.

FIGURE 23. MEASURED: A) SURFACE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH (SCS); B) ELASTICITY MODULUS (E).

TABLE 4. RESULTS OF THE SURFACE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH (SCS) AND ELASTICITY MODULUS (E).

Beam	SCS (Mpa)	UPV (km/s)	E (MPa)
Reference concrete	69	4,9	59,3
Lime ash concrete	64	5,0	58,6

Results of the ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) showed that concrete is of excellent quality and has a similar performance either with lime ash and with natural filler.

2.2. Portuguese regulation

Concrete elements (columns and beams) applied on this demo pilot are covered by EN 13225 standard, where the basic criteria and evaluation conformity are indicated.

Columns are reinforced concrete products, but the beams are considered reinforced and prestressed concrete products. These products have a minimum of demanded concrete compressive strength class. Columns concrete class must be equal or higher than a C20/25 concrete and beams needs a C30/37 class, respectively.

Aggregates for precast concrete are covered by EN 12620 standard, where properties and test method for characterization of aggregates are indicated. In Portugal, there is also a guide for the use of non-recycled aggregates in concrete (E 467 Specification) that indicates the minimum requirements.

When there is only concrete as waste, this has the EWC 17 01 01 code, according to decision 2014/9557UE of December 18th. In Portugal, there is Decree law n.º 46/2008, March 12th that establishes the regime of operations of CDW management, but was changed by decree law n.º 73/2011 june 17th.

Specification E 471 provides recommendations and establishes minimum requirements for the use of coarse recycled aggregates covered by standard NP EN 12620 on production of hydraulic binders' concrete. It does not set demands and rules for fine aggregates recycled aggregates. Concrete wastes to be used in concrete as recycled coarse aggregates must follow recommendation and comply with minimum requirements of Specification E 471.

In environmental terms, recycled aggregates must comply with leachate requirements for inert landfill, according to Decree law 183/2009, August 10th. If inert waste criteria does not comply, wastes must be deposited in a landfill for non-dangerous and dangerous waste.

3. Circular case 1b: Road pavement

Planned road pavement with and without PPI wastes (dregs and grits) was built in March of 2020 and it is located at Navigator company facilities in Cacia Aveiro (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Local of application of the bituminous mixture.

The report "D5.2 - Implementation of Circular Case 1" doesn't show a full description of pilot execution due to unexpected rains in February 2020 that have delayed the road implementation process at Navigator plant.

Figure 25 up to 30 show the pilot execution from production in bituminous mixture central to the final application at Navigator's road. In the bituminous central, dregs and grits were integrated into the bituminous mixture (Figure 25) and then both mixtures were transported in a tipper truck from the central to the application site in the Navigator (NVG) industrial site (Figure 26).

b)

FIGURE 25. ASPHALT MIXING PLANT: A) INTEGRATION OF WASTES (GRITS AND DREGS) INTO THE BITUMINOUS MIXTURE; B) BITUMINOUS PRODUCTION

FIGURE 26. DISCHARGED BITUMINOUS MIXTURE TO A TIPPER TRUCK.

While the manufacture of the bituminous mixture was taking place at the central, Megavia (project partner) workers went ahead with the setup preparation of the road (Figure 27) to be able to receive the different bituminous mixtures, at the NVG facilities.

FIGURE 27. PREPARATION OF ROAD BASE TO RECEIVE SURFACE LAYER.

MEGAVIA used an asphalt paver for spreading the bituminous mixture along the specific road stretch (Figure 28). Then a tandem roller was used to compact the layer (Figure 29).

FIGURE 28. HOT BITUMINOUS MIXTURE DISCHARGE AND APPLICATION OF MIXTURE BY ASPHALT PAVER.

FIGURE 29. COMPACTION WORKS BY TANDEM ROLLER.

Figure 30 shows the result of different bituminous mixtures sections and Figure 31 shows the final execution scheme of CC1B). Different colours identify the type of bituminous mixture (green is the reference bituminous mixture (bm), pink is the stretch with grits and light blue is the one with dregs).

FIGURE 30. FINAL RESULT OF REFERENCE, DREGS AND GRITS BITUMINOUS MIXTURE SECTION.

FIGURE 31. FINAL EXECUTION PLANT OF CC1B IMPLEMENTATION.

3.1. Monitoring

3.1.1. Environmental monitoring.

The environmental compatibility of reference mixture and mixtures with dregs and grits was assessed in terms of leaching behaviour. This procedure was made in situ and in laboratory with RAIZ guidance.

In situ, the drainage system has gullies (Figure 32) that are connected to the residual rainwater system and connected to the natural ditch willow.

FIGURE 32. GULLIES WHERE RAINWATER WAS COLLECTED; B) POSITIONS WHERE WATER WAS COLLECTED TO BE ANALYSED.

The rainwater was drained of the surface layer and then proceeded to the gullies to be collected. The main water source was rainwater, however, and due the low rainfall periods during the environmental monitoring, the rain was simulated by watering the road and the samples were collected immediately. Table 5 shows the leachate results from rainfall for different road sections.

TABLE 5. RESULTS OF THE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE WATER FROM THE DRAINAGE SYSTEM.

Parameter	Unit	Month 0	Month 3			Month 6			Month 9			Month 12			Limit DL 183/2009 (mg/l), with L/S =10l/kg (Inert waste)
		Before demo installation	Ref	Dregs	Grits										
Chloride	mg/l	5,6	17,1	16,5	16,6	20,3	19,6	19,0	16,9	17,0	16,9	16,4	16,1	16,3	80
Cr total	µg/L	0,90	<0,40(L.Q.)	<0,003(L.Q.)	<0,003(L.Q.)	0,004	0,05								
Fluoride	mg/L	<0,200(L.Q.)				0,23	0,22	0,33				<0,200(L.Q.)	<0,200(L.Q.)	<0,200(L.Q.)	1
Phenol index	mg/L	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	<0,005(L.Q.)	0,1
Sulphate	mg/L	11,97				26,00	25,83	22,53				16,60	15,70	14,53	100
Cu	mg(Cu)/L	0,03				0,04	0,08	0,06				0,04	0,03	0,04	0,2
Zn	mg(Zn)/L	0,05				0,30	0,12	0,83				0,20	0,49	1,08	0,4
Pb	mg(Pb)/L	0,01	0,003	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,0044	<0,002(L.Q.)	0,0024	0,003	0,006	0,02	0,05
Hg	mg(Hg)/L	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	<0,01(L.Q.)	0,001
Cd	mg(Cd)/L	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	<0,0005(L.Q.)	0,004
Ni	mg(Ni)/L	0,01			0,00	0,01	0,01	0,01				0,005	0,004	0,01	0,04
Cr	mg(Cr)/L	0,004	<0,003(L.Q.)	<0,003(L.Q.)	0,01	0,01	0,004	0,01	0,003	<0,003(L.Q.)	<0,003(L.Q.)	<0,003(L.Q.)	<0,003(L.Q.)	0,004	0,05
Ba	mg(Ba)/L	0,01				0,10	0,08	0,20				0,08	0,06	0,02	2
As	mg(As)/L	0,002	0,001	0,001	0,002	0,018	0,018	0,002	0,016	0,016	0,016	0,146	0,012	0,002	0,05
Sb	mg(Sb)/L	0,001				0,002	<0,001(L.Q.)	0,00				<0,001(L.Q.)	<0,001(L.Q.)	0,004	0,006
Se	mg(Se)/L	<0,003(L.Q.)				<0,003(L.Q.)	<0,003(L.Q.)	<0,003(L.Q.)				<0,003(L.Q.)	<0,003(L.Q.)	<0,003(L.Q.)	0,01

For each specific road stretch with different formulation, there is at least one gully (Figure 32b) to collect the water samples. The collection was made monthly and accordingly to Portuguese Decree Law nº 183/2009. The first collection was made before the installation of CC1b) demonstrator for control purposes.

For many parameters (phenol index, mercury, cadmium and selenium), the concentration in the leachate was below the detection limit and far below the limit values in all field samples. For other parameters (chloride, chromium, zinc, lead, nickel, barium, arsenic, antimony), results were above quantification limit, however much far below the limit value allowed.

Throughout the monitoring period (one year), chlorides were evaluated monthly, as can be seen in table 6. The application of the road induces the increase of chloride content, independently of the type of mixture, but the content complies with the limit of the regulating Decree law nº 183/2009 for inert wastes.

TABLE 6. RESULTS OF THE CHLORIDES IN THE WATER SAMPLES FROM IN SITU.

Month	Clorides (mg/l)			Limit DL 183/2009 (mg/L), with L/S =10l/kg (Inert Waste)
	Ref	Dregs	Grits	
0	5,6			80
1	16,5	16,4	15,7	
2	15,5	16,2	16,1	
3	17,1	16,5	16,6	
4	16,7	16,5	17,2	
5	18,4	18,5	18,5	
6	20,3	19,6	19,0	
7	14,5	14,6	16,5	

8	12,9	12,3	16,8
9	16,9	17,0	16,9
10	16,8	17,0	16,9
11	17,7	17,4	16,5
12	16,4	16,1	16,3

The samples that were collected during the pilot execution, were used to evaluate at laboratorial scale the eluates values following the decree law n° 183/2009. About 50mg of bituminous samples were dissolved in a volume 10 times of the samples weight with ionized water (500ml).

Samples (Figure 33) were mixed in an orbital shaker during 5, 24, 48, 76 and 96 hours. After those periods, the samples were vacuum filtrated with filter paper to remove suspended materials. Table 7 shows the eluate results from laboratory test, namely conductivity, pH, CQO, chlorides and heavy metals (cadmium, chromium, copper, nickel, zinc and lead).

FIGURE 33. ENVIRONMENTAL CONTROL FOR BITUMINOUS MIXTURE IN THE LABORATORY.

TABLE 7. RESULTS OF THE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE WATER IN LABORATORY

Bituminous Mixture	pH	CQO (mg/L)	Conductivity (µS/cm)	Testing time (h)	Chlorides (ALS) (mg/L)	Metals (ALS) (mg/L)					
						Cadmium	Chromium Total	Copper	Nickel	Lead	Zinc
Grits	9,04	21,5	45,63	5	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	< 0,006 (L.Q.)	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
	9,36	< 15 (L.Q.)	41,83	24	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	0,0065 ± 0,0018	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
	9,55	< 15 (L.Q.)	51,03	48	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	< 0,006 (L.Q.)	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
	9,49	< 15 (L.Q.)	48,73	72	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	< 0,006 (L.Q.)	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
9,52	< 15 (L.Q.)	48,67	96	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	< 0,006 (L.Q.)	0,00123 ± 0,00034	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)	
Dregs	9,79	< 15 (L.Q.)	111,37	5	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	< 0,006 (L.Q.)	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
	9,82	< 15 (L.Q.)	185,20	24	1,04	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	< 0,006 (L.Q.)	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
	9,89	< 15 (L.Q.)	210,67	48	1,26	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	0,0068 ± 0,0019	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
	10,24	< 15 (L.Q.)	251,67	72	1,36	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	0,0100 ± 0,0026	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
10,14	< 15 (L.Q.)	243,00	96	1,28	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	< 0,006 (L.Q.)	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)	
Reference	8,80	< 15 (L.Q.)	38,63	5	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	< 0,006 (L.Q.)	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
	9,02	< 15 (L.Q.)	44,80	24	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	< 0,006 (L.Q.)	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
	9,12	< 15 (L.Q.)	46,07	48	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	0,0080 ± 0,0022	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	0,0206 ± 0,0058
	9,30	< 15 (L.Q.)	44,57	72	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	0,0065 ± 0,0018	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)
9,42	< 15 (L.Q.)	45,13	96	< 1,00 (L.Q.)	< 0,0005 (L.Q.)	< 0,003 (L.Q.)	< 0,006 (L.Q.)	< 0,001 (L.Q.)	< 0,002 (L.Q.)	< 0,02 (L.Q.)	
Limit DL 183/2009 (mg/L), with L/S = 10l/kg (Inert Waste)	-	-	-	-	80	0,004	0,05	0,2	0,04	0,05	0,4

L.Q. – Below to quantification limit;

The tested mixtures samples fulfilled the Portuguese regulation for leaching behaviour, with concentrations in the leachate far below the limit values.

3.1.2. Technical monitoring.

Reference bituminous mixture uses natural aggregates (gravel, crushed limestone, filler) and binder which all have CE marking. In other words, density, particle size and harmful fines are also declared on the product technical sheet. Thus, dregs, grits and the fine aggregates were characterized in the laboratory to observe similarities and differences between them. Figure 34 shows the visual aspect between crushed limestone fine aggregate to be replaced and the PPI wastes, dregs and grits.

FIGURE 34. VISUAL COMPARATIVE BETWEEN DREGS, GRITS AND CRUSHED STONE.

Figure 35 presents the particle size distribution for dregs, grits and limestone crushed stone. This analysis demonstrates that dregs and grits present a comparable size grading to the crushed limestone.

FIGURE 35. PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF DREGS, GRITS AND CRUSHED STONE.

Fine particles quality and particle density of dregs and grits were evaluated in order to regard the requirements of the guidebook for a road surface layer.

Density needs to be measured and declared, but blue methylene value must be less or equal 10 g/kg for fine aggregates quality control. Table 8 shows the fine aggregates quality and density results for dregs, grits and crushed limestone. These results showed that the used PPI wastes are suitable for the requirements of the national guidebook.

TABLE 8. FINE AGGREGATE QUALITY AND PARTICLE DENSITY FOR DREGS, GRITS AND CRUSHED LIMESTONE.

	Grits	Dregs	Crushed Limestone (0/4)	Standard	Guidebook limits for AC 14 surface
Apparent particle density (Mg/m ³)	2630	2630	2640	NP EN 1097-6	-
Quality fines (blue methylene) (g/kg)	0,2	3,6	4	NP EN 933-9	≤10

Crushed limestone was partially replaced by dregs or grits in bituminous mixture with dregs or grits, respectively. Table 9 shows the weight percentages of each aggregate to produce the different bituminous mixture to be used in the demo pilot. These bituminous mixtures respected a particle size range for an AC 14 surface, that is defined in the *Infraestruturas de Portugal* guidebook, as can be seen in Figure 36.

TABLE 9. BITUMINOUS MIXTURE COMPOSITION USED IN THE PILOT.

Fraction	Reference (%)	Dregs (%)	Grits (%)
Coarse aggregate (6/14)	52	52	52
Crushed granite (0/5)	22	22	22
Crushed limestone (0/4)	22	18	18
Filler	4	4	4
Dregs	0	4	0
Grits	0	0	4
Bitumen	4,9	5	4,9

FIGURE 36. PARTICLE SIZE CURVE OF THE AGGREGATE MIXTURE USED IN THE MANUFACTURE OF THE BITUMINOUS MIXTURES AND THE LIMITS IMPOSED BY THE GUIDEBOOK.

During the pavements works of the different segments, bituminous mixtures were collected for a control quality in laboratory (Figure 37). Afterwards, Marshal test specimens were produced to verify and monitor:

- Particle size distribution – sieving method, according to EN 933-1
- Binder content of bituminous mixtures, according to ASTM D2172
- Maximum density determination, according to EN 12697-5 (method A)
- Bulk density, according to EN 12697-6 (Method B)

- Volumetric properties (voids, voids content in the mineral aggregate and voids in the mineral aggregate filled with binder), according to EN 12697-8
- Marshall characteristics (stability, flow and Marshall quotient), according EN 12697-34
- Conserved strenght index, according to MIL-STD-620A (method 104)

FIGURE 37. LABORATORY CONTROL FOR BITUMINOUS MIXTURE.

Table 10 and Figure 38 show the results of the parameters evaluated in the laboratory. These parameters were evaluated in July and August of 2020.

All parameters of different bituminous mixtures comply with the limits of the IP guidebook, apart from voids and conserved strength of the bituminous mixture with dregs.

TABLE 10. CHARACTERISTICS OF BITUMINOUS MIXTURE IN JULY AND AUGUST OF 2020.

Samples	Standard	Grits	Dregs	Guidebook limits	Standard
Density	2357	2351	2336	- (Mg/m ³)	EN 12697-6
Maximum density	2471	2465	2476	- (Mg/m ³)	EN 12697-5
Air voids content (VM)	4,6	4,6	5,7	3 a 5 %	EN 12697-8
Voids content in the mineral aggregate	15,8	15,8	17,0	≥ 14 %	EN 12697-8
Voids in the mineral aggregate filled with binder	70,9	70,9	66,8	- (%)	EN 12697-8
Flow	3,7	3,4	3,6	2 ≤ F ≤ 4 mm	EN 12697-34
Stability	16,3	14,7	15,3	7,5 ≤ S ≤ 15(*) kN	EN 12697-34
Marshall quotient	4,4	4,3	4,2	≥ 3 kN/mm	EN 12697-34
Conserved strength	100 (110)	95	77	>80 %	MIL STD 620 (method 104)
%binder	4,9	4,9	4,9	±0,3 %	Reflux method

(*) for granitic rock aggregates maximum stability must be 21kN

FIGURE 38. RESULTS OF THE PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION IN JULY AND AUGUST.

In November and December of 2020, new specimens were produced and tested in the laboratory (Table 11 and Figure 39). All parameters of different bituminous mixtures comply with the limits of the IP guidebook, apart from the voids content and the conserved strength for the bituminous mixture with dregs, but very slightly. Voids in the bituminous mixture with dregs has a slight decrease due to compaction of the bituminous mixture.

TABLE 11. CHARACTERISTICS OF BITUMINOUS MIXTURE IN NOVEMBER-DECEMBER OF 2020

Samples	Standard	Grits	Dregs	Guidebook limits	Standard
Density	2374	2380	2348	-	EN 12697-6
Maximum density	2465	2483	2479	-	EN 12697-5
Air voids content (VM)	3,7	4,2	5,3	3 a 5 %	EN 12697-8
Voids content in the mineral aggregate	15,0	15,5	16,7	≥ 14 %	EN 12697-8
Voids in the mineral aggregate filled with binder	75,3	73,2	68,4	-	EN 12697-8
Flow	4,2	4,0	3,9	2 ≤ F ≤ 4 mm	EN 12697-34
Stability	23,8	18,6	18,2	7,5 ≤ S ≤ 15 kN	EN 12697-34
Marshall quotient	5,6	4,7	4,6	≥ 3 kN/mm	EN 12697-34
Conserved strength	90	93	77	>80 %	MIL STD 620 (method 104)
%binder	5,2	5,1	4,7	±0,3	Reflux method

FIGURE 39. RESULTS OF THE PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION IN NOVEMBER AND DECEMBER OF 2020.

In situ, 3 cores (Figure 40) were extracted from each road section to evaluate voids, binder content and aggregate mix gradation, density and maximum density. All cores showed two bituminous mixture layers, as can be seen in Figure 41. First bituminous mixture layer was already built before the application of the surface layer of the pilot. All cores were extracted on the roadside and both layers didn't turn off by its binding. In other words, there is a good adherence between bituminous mixtures layers.

FIGURE 40. STAGES OF CORES EXTRACTION.

FIGURE 41. PAVEMENT STRUCTURE OF THE BOUND LAYERS (CORES).

TABLE 12. CHARACTERISTICS OF BITUMINOUS MIXTURE ON CORES.

Samples	Reference			Grits			Dregs		
	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III
Maximum density (kg/m ³)	2422			2452			2409		
Density (kg/m ³)	2215	2260	2247	2296	2273	2248	2275	2297	2294
% soluble binder (%)	4,6			4,5			4,6		
Thickness (mm)	62	63	56	51	40	42	53	58	52
Thickness, avg (mm)	60			44			54		
Air voids content (VM) (%)	8,5	6,7	7,2	6,3	7,3	8,3	5,6	4,6	4,8
Volumetric bitumen content (TVB) (%)	9,9	10,1	10,0	10,0	9,9	9,8	10,2	10,3	10,2

Voids content in the mineral aggregate (VMA)	18,4	16,8	17,2	16,4	17,2	18,2	15,7	14,9	15,0
Degree of saturation in bitumen (GS) (%)	53,7	60,2	58,2	61,3	57,6	54,1	64,7	68,8	68,3
Degree of Compaction "maximum density"	91,5	93,3	92,8	93,7	92,7	91,7	94,4	95,4	95,2

FIGURE 42. RESULTS OF THE PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION IN CORES.

Table 12 and Figure 42 show the results of some parameters on the extracted cores.

After 6 months and 1 year service, visual inspections were also made to identify possible degradations that might appear on this flexible road pavement. Typically different distress, namely transversal and longitudinal cracking, fatigue cracking, delamination, loss of coarse aggregates, segregation (ravelling), bitumen exudation, polished aggregates, settlements, pothole, patching and patch deterioration, rutting, longitudinal irregularity in adherence could appear.

Table 13 shows the anomalies that were identified during visual inspections. All sections have a small rutting and segregation (ravelling). In addition, grits section presents a transversal small cracking that appeared near the transition of flexible and rigid pavement. The heavy trucks passage in this zone can generate this kind of degradation. Nevertheless, these are not considered significant degradation considering the daily traffic of this road.

TABLE 13. ANOMALIES IDENTIFIED DURING VISUAL INSPECTION

Distress	Standard	Dregs	Grits
Rutting			
segregation (ravelling)			

Transversal crack			
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The surface quality of the pavement can be evaluated through a quality index (QI). This index has an expression that is related to different types of degradations:

$$QI = -0.002139 \times R^{2-0.03 \times (C+S+P)^{0.5} + 5 \times e^{-0.0002598 \times IRI/2}}$$

where:

IRI- Longitudinal irregularity of pavement (International Roughness Index (mm/km);

R – is mean depth of rutting (mm)

C – is area with cracking and fatigue cracking (m²/100m²)

S – is area with Pothole (m²/100m²)

P– is area with Patching and Patch Deterioration (m²/100m²)

When the quality index is between 0 and 2 is bad, when is between 2 and 2,5 is reasonable and between 3.5 and 5 is considered good.

During the visual inspection, the pathologies were classified according to degradation intensity and extension. Table 14 shows the identification of distress of flexible road pavements.

TABLE 14. IDENTIFIER OF DISTRESS OF FLEXIBLE ROAD PAVEMENTS

Distress type	Degradation level	Description of degradation level	Affected area/ Adopted value
	Level 1	- Isolate crack	0,5 m x affected length

1 Transversal and longitudinal cracking	Level 2	- Significant longitudinal crack, ramified with possible loss of material (2mm<opening<4mm)	2,0m x affected length
	Level 3	-Severe longitudinal crack, ramified or slightly interconnected with loss of material (opening>4mm) - Transversal crack of any severity	Section width x affected length
2 Fatigue cracking	Level 1	Mesh of small cracks without fine segregation (crack opening<2mm and mesh>20cm)	Section width x affected length
	Level 2	Mesh of cracks with any dimension and material loss (crack opening<2mm and mesh<20cm or 2mm<crack<4mm and mesh of any type or crack opening>4mm and mesh>40cm)	Section width x affected length
	Level 3	Mesh of big cracks with fine segregation (crack opening>4mm and mesh>40cm)	Section width x affected length
3 Delamination, loss of coarse aggregates, segregation (ravelling), bitumen exudation, polished aggregates, settlements	Level 1	Distress width<30cm	0,5 m x affected. length
	Level 2	30cm<distress width<100cm	2,0 m x affected length
	Level 3	Distress width>100cm or several distresses (of any width) in the same transversal section	Section width x affected length
4 Pothole	Level 1	Maximum depth<2cm	0,5 m x affected length
	Level 2	2cm<maximum depth<4cm	2,0 2 m x affected length
	Level 3	Maximum depth>4cm or several pothole (of any width) in the same transversal section	Section width x affected length
5 Patching and Patch Deterioration	Level 1	Well executed patches	¼ section width x affected length
	Level 2	Patches with poor execution quality or joints bad executed	½ section width x affected length
	Level 3	Bad executed patches	Section width x affected length
6 Rutting	Level 1	Maximum depth<10mm	10mm
	Level 2	10mm<maximum depth<30mm	25mm
	Level 3	Maximum depth>30mm	40mm
7 Longitudinal irregularity	-	Value of Value of international roughness index	IRI (mm/km)

Table 15 shows the methodology to quantify the IRI value, where this value was calculated through of weighted average between degradation levels and their extension.

TABLE 15. METHODOLOGY TO QUANTIFY THE IRI VALUE

Degradation	Condition	Level	IRI
Cracking and Fatigue cracking	\leq , and	1	Type 1 IRI= 1500 mm/km
Delamination, etc	\leq , and	1	
Rutting	\leq	1	
			Type 2 IRI= 2500 mm/km
Cracking and Fatigue cracking	$=$, or	3	Type 1 IRI= 3500 mm/km
Delamination, etc	$=$, and	3	
Rutting	\geq	2	

Table 16 shows the surface quality of the pavements and there is no difference between the different sections (reference, dregs and grits). All sections show good quality and have the same type of degradation (Table 13).

TABLE 16. SURFACE QUALITY OF THE PILOT (ONE YEAR AFTER SERVICE)

	Standard	Dregs	Grits
C	0	0	1
S	18	2	23
P	0	0	0
IRI	1500	1500	1500
R	1	3	0
QI	4,0	4,1	4
Quality	Good	Good	Good

3.2. Portuguese regulation

Aggregates for bituminous mixture are covered by EN 13043 standard where properties and test method for characterization of aggregates are indicated. Although EN 13108-1 standard specifies requirements for mixture of the mix group Asphalt Concrete for use on roads, airfields, and other track field areas. In Portugal, IP authority has three guidebooks for paving, to define the material characteristics, constructive methods, categories and measurement criteria. The constructive methods guidebook defines mainly the production tolerance for binder and aggregates and layers executions, although material characteristics indicates the requirements for aggregates and bituminous mixture.

When there is only bituminous mixture as waste, this has the EWC 17 03 02 code according to decision 2014/9557UE of December 18th. In Portugal, there is Decree law n.º 46/2008 March 12th that establishes the regime of operations of CDW management, but was changed by decree law n.º 73/2011 June 17th.

The guidebook of *Infraestruturas de Portugal* (national regulations) considers three different methodologies of recycled mix. One methodology is “in situ” and the production temperature is cold. The two other solutions are produced in a processing central. The only difference is the production temperature (hot or semi-warm).

In the case of using recycled aggregates on bituminous mixture, there is also E472 national specification, which classifies reclaimed asphalt materials covered by EN 13108-8 and provides guidelines for their used in hot mix recycled asphalt.

4. Conclusions

The Circular Case demonstration pilots occurring in Portugal were finished and monitored during WP5 schedule. The 2 pilots were established in place very well according to expectations and programming of the project, except for the bituminous mixture applications that suffered a week delay due to atmospheric conditions (unforeseen rain).

Throughout 1-year, the monitoring was performed at the environmental and technical level, from laboratory to the on-site inspection and accompanied by the respective visual inspection through one year. The lockdown caused by the Covid-19 pandemic caused a delay on the monitoring activities that had to be compensated in the end of the task in 2021.

The major conclusion for both CC1 pilots is that the incorporation of wastes were quite successful and that they can be used as alternative raw materials to natural ones in precast concrete (lime ash as a filler replacement) and in road pavements (dregs and grits as a fine aggregate replacement), preventing not only landfill disposal of these wastes but also savings in the use of natural raw materials in the construction sector. Although lime ash does not need a pre-treatment before application in precast concrete. On the other hand, the use of dregs and grits in road pavement applications needs a drying and grinding pre-treatment operation in order for them to be used.

Finally, the features and characteristics of the targeted construction products were not hindered or modified by the introduction of these wastes after long term monitoring.

All data needed for WP6, WP7 and WP8 was and will continue to be given to WPs leaders concerning the results and operation of this WP5 work and conclusions.

5. References

Internal sources (Paperchain Deliverables):

1. Deliverable 2.1: Baseline Reporte – PPI waste streams valorisation potential.
2. Deliverable 8.1: Report on transition assessment for circular economy processes.
3. Deliverable 4.1: Report on solutions feasibility and constraints.
4. Deliverable 2.2: Quality assurance procedures for the circular model demos.

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